

A Stylized 3D General Electric PRISM Benchmark Problem

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ABSTRACT

A set of 3D General Electric Power Reactor Innovative Small Module (GE-PRISM) sodium-cooled fast reactor benchmark problems is developed in this paper. The configurations include an uncontrolled case with all control rods withdrawn, a controlled case with all control rods inserted, and a critical case with some control rods inserted. The benchmark problems retain detailed geometric and material information of the Metal fuel, liquid sodium coolant, duct gaps, wire spacers, Boron Carbide (B_4C) absorber, stainless steel alloy HT9 cladding for uncontrolled, critical, and controlled assembly configurations, and faithfully adheres to those design specifications that are available publicly.

Keywords: SFR, Benchmark, Sodium-Cooled, OpenMC, PRISM

1. INTRODUCTION

The Power Reactor Innovative Small Module (PRISM) [1] is a sodium cooled fast reactor (SFR) that dates back to General Electric (GE) efforts in the 1980s to develop an SFR design for commercial deployment as part of the U.S. Advanced Liquid Metal Reactor (ALMR) [2] [3] DOE program. In 2006, GE Hitachi revisited the design as part of the DOE's Global Nuclear Energy Partnership [1] as a proposed pathway to produce electricity from recycled nuclear fuel. This work is motivated by the desire to add to the Particle Transport modeling test suite to enable full-core benchmarking, as well as preliminary work towards testing the implementation of a novel reactor heat sink device [4] in partnership with Texas A&M and INL. This work will therefore form the foundation for integration with thermal fluids analysis in future work for a more complete system analysis. Here, three PRISM neutronics configurations were developed – uncontrolled (ARO), critical (SRI), and controlled (ARI) – to generate accurate heating profiles for coupled neutron-photon transport calculations using OpenMC. Detailed core specifications and benchmark results are presented with a treatment of any design simplifications or assumptions.

The paper is organized as follows. The assumptions and considerations used for developing each benchmark problem are presented in Section 2. A detailed specification of the materials and geometry for driver fuel, blanket fuel, control and shielding assemblies as well as the full-core layout is presented in Section 3. OpenMC Neutronics modeling run parameters and solutions are presented in Section 4.

2. ASSUMPTIONS AND SIMPLIFICATIONS

The PRISM design is a privately developed project belonging to GE Hitachi. Therefore, many exact details relevant to a reactor model are not available and therefore need to be estimated from similar reactor designs. In this section the relevant assumptions and simplifications that were made to develop a complete benchmark are outlined with a treatment of the specific limitations those bring.

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2.1. Fuel Composition

Limited details are available about the true material composition of fuel in the driver and blanket assemblies for this Metal configuration of the PRISM core. Isotopics used for this benchmark work are based on freshly loaded fuel compositions from [1] and [5]. Several assumptions were made in those works that are worth restating for completeness here. Firstly, these benchmarks model freshly loaded fuel compositions. Therefore, it is assumed that the fuel does not contain any fission products and the internal and radial blanket assemblies have the same material composition. Secondly, while many variants of the PRISM design were explored – namely low conversion ratio UNF actinide recycle, unity conversion ratio (isobreeder), and high conversion ratio (breeder) variants [1]– for these benchmark problems we assume that minor actinide and non-fissile plutonium masses are equal, and that the ratio of non-fissile to fissile plutonium was 1:4. Thirdly, in the absence of precise minor actinide isotope fractions, we use specifications from a similar Helium-cooled fast reactor design [6]. Lastly, we assume true material densities are less than literature theoretical densities. As the exact fuel densities are unknown, a reasonable estimate of ~88% of the specified theoretical density of 15.05 g/cm^3 is used.

2.2. Containment Vessel & Secondary Systems

Rough configuration specifications for the containment vessel, heat exchanger, and secondary coolant loops are provided in literature [7]. For the purposes of this work, for which a consideration of transient analysis or thermal hydraulic coupling framework is out of scope, everything outside of the shielding assembly region is treated as vacuum. This is a valid assumption for the development of a neutron-photon transport benchmark that does not treat 1) Neutronic effects of secondary systems which is negligible, or 2) an integrated Neutronics Thermal-Fluids modeling framework for temperature Doppler feedback and varying material composition. The Gas Expansion Module which the PRISM design uses is modeled as a steady-state assembly.

2.3. Temperature Data

As a standalone Neutronics model uncoupled from thermal fluid dependence, cell temperature for driver, blanket, reflector, shielding and GEM assemblies was estimated from [5] and [7]. There, important thermal parameters – outlet temperatures, peak fuel temperatures for internal and radial fuel assemblies, etc., - are generated for simplified and extrapolated PRISM benchmarks for transient accident scenario analysis. With many key design parameters not publicly available, estimates for cell temperature data represent reasonable extrapolations from the documented design specifications as well as similar sodium-cooled SMR designs.

3. CORE SPECIFICATION

The PRISM reactor module was designed to have a rated thermal power of 840 MW and an electrical output of 311 MW, with an overall thermal efficiency of 37%. The core is arranged as a series of fuel, control, reflector, and shielding hexagonal assemblies. Freshly loaded driver fuel is composed of 69.5% Uranium, 17.1% Plutonium, 3.4% Minor Actinides, and 10% Zirconium with a theoretical density of 15.05 g/cm^3 . Detailed isotopic breakdown for both driver and blanket fuel is given in *Table III*. Core parameters are summarized in *Table I*.

Table I. PRISM Core

Parameter	Value
Core Thermal Power	840 MW
Thermal Efficiency	37%
Fuel Type	Metal
Reflector Material	HT9
Core Height	1.02 meters
Coolant	Liquid Na

3.1. Radial and Axial Layout

The radial configuration of the Metal PRISM core is given in **Error! Reference source not found.** The core lattice consists of driver fuel assemblies, layered in rings with internal and then radial blanket fuel assemblies. Control assemblies are arranged symmetrically about the inner core, with Gas Expansion Module (GEM) assemblies on the periphery of the fuel region. The fuel region is surrounded by two rings of reflector assemblies, and then a ring of shielding assemblies. The total number of assemblies is given in *Table II*.

Table II. Assembly Count

Assembly	Assembly Count	Pins-per-Assembly
Driver Fuel	138	217
Blanket Fuel	97	127
Control	12	61
Reflector	126	61
Shielding	72	7
GEM	6	N/A

Figure 1. Assembly Layout of Metal PRISM core.

3.2. Fuel Assembly Configuration

Two configurations of fuel assemblies are used in the PRISM design – 138 driver fuel assemblies, 49 internal blanket assemblies, and 48 radial blanket assemblies. Driver fuel assemblies have 271 pins arranged in a triangular lattice. Geometrical specifications of each driver fuel pin are in *Table IV*, and material composition in *Table III*. Internal and radial blanket assemblies have 127 pins arranged in a seven-ring triangular lattice. It should be noted that freshly loaded fuel material composition is identical in internal and radial blanket fuel, before varying depletion characteristics across the core alter material composition.

Figure 2. Driver Fuel Assembly (left) & Blanket Fuel Assembly (right).

Table III. Driver & Blanket Fuel Composition of PRISM Metal Core.

Nuclide	Driver Fuel Wt.%	Blanket Fuel Wt.%
U^{234}	0.004	0.005
U^{235}	0.494	0.605
U^{238}	68.955	84.462
Pu^{238}	0.082	0.020
Pu^{239}	12.241	2.936
Pu^{240}	3.103	0.744
Pu^{241}	1.457	0.349
Pu^{242}	0.240	0.058
Np^{237}	1.713	0.411
Am^{241}	1.421	0.341
Am^{243}	0.291	0.070
Zr	10.000	10.000

Freshly loaded fuel in internal and radial blankets is identical - composed of approximately natural Uranium and significantly less fertile Plutonium content compared to driver fuel. Rods consist of fuel slugs with reflector endcaps and a gas plenum which serves as buffer space for fission byproduct gas release. As several fuel designs for the PRISM reactor were developed for different purposes – actinide recycling, isobreeder and breeder configurations [1] – we refer to previous work [5] and reasonable

estimates of densities, cell temperatures, and other quantities of interest. A schematic of a single fuel rod is given in *Figure 3*.

Figure 3. Schematic of PRISM fuel rod [1].

Table IV. Driver & Blanket Assembly and Pin Geometry Summary.

	Driver	Blanket
<i>Pin Count</i>	271	127
<i>Pin Rings per Assembly</i>	10	7
<i>Assembly Pitch (cm)</i>	16.14200	16.14200
<i>Duct Gap (cm)</i>	0.43200	0.43200
<i>Duct Wall Thickness (cm)</i>	0.39400	0.39400
<i>Pin Pitch (cm)</i>	0.90687	1.32542
<i>Fuel Pin Radius (cm)</i>	0.27385	0.50230
<i>Gap Thickness (cm)</i>	0.04225	0.04230
<i>Clad Thickness (cm)</i>	0.05590	0.05590
<i>Clad Radius – inner (cm)</i>	0.31610	0.54460
<i>Clad Radius – outer (cm)</i>	0.37200	0.60050

3.3. Control & Shielding Assembly Configuration

Reactivity control for nominal startup, reactivity control during the cycle phase and shutdown is accomplished with B_4C control rods [1]. Control assemblies are composed of six rings of cylindrical control rods arranged in a triangular lattice surrounded by cladding and sodium coolant. For the three modeled cases, the uncontrolled case has all rods withdrawn, the controlled case all rods inserted, and the critical case some of the radial rods withdrawn to achieve criticality. As the location of withdrawn/inserted rods substantially impacts fission densities, flux profile, and many other quantities of interest, for the exact control assembly configuration refer to the OpenMC input files attached to this works submission on the Georgia Tech Digital Repository.

3.4. Gas Expansion Module

The PRISM design makes use of Gas Expansion Module (GEM) assemblies arranged on the periphery of the fuel region [7]. GEM is a leakage-based reactivity control mechanism assembly is filled with an inert gas. Functioning much like a piston, coolant flow pressure causes the GEM to be filled with coolant. Inversely, when coolant pressure decreases the gas expands, pushing coolant down, and thereby increasing leakage from the core. For all three benchmark cases developed in this work Helium (He) with a density of 0.0001786 g/cm^3 is used. As a reactivity control feature with geometry and material composition necessarily changing with coolant flow pressure during reactor operation modeling this behavior dynamically would require thermal hydraulic feedback and transient modeling significantly

beyond the scope of this work. Instead, a reasonable estimate of steady-state parameters is used to model this component within the framework of a standalone Neutronics model.

4. SOLUTION TO BENCHMARK PROBLEMS

OpenMC [8] was used to model three Core configurations – uncontrolled (ARO), critical (SRI), and controlled (ARI) cases – to calculate the core eigenvalue and a fuel pin heating map of the core. Due to the symmetry of the problem, only a 1/12 radial wedge was run while imposing reflective boundary conditions on the two wedge surfaces. A photon transport enabled calculation for each benchmark ran on a 48-core allocation on the GT PACE HPC for eleven hours and tallied heating for both driver and blanket fuel. Heating densities (normalized by pin volumes) are overlaid on the geometry in *Figure 2*. Reference OpenMC input files, output parsing scripts, and solutions to the benchmark problems are provided with this paper’s submission to the Georgia Tech Digital Repository.

Figure 2. PRISM Geometry Plot with Fuel Pin Heating ($\frac{\text{eV}}{\text{source particle cm}^3}$) Tally overlay (SRI).

For the uncontrolled case (ARO) case OpenMC calculated a combined average core eigenvalue of 0.9566 ± 0.0003 . Similarly, for controlled (ARI) and critical (SRI) cases OpenMC calculated eigenvalues of 1.0385 ± 0.0002 and 1.000341 ± 0.0002 . These results are summarized in *Table V*.

Table V. Summary of k_{eff} .

Case	Core Eigenvalue
ARO	1.0385 ± 0.0002
SRI	1.0003 ± 0.0002
ARI	0.9566 ± 0.0003

Fission density was tallied in driver and blanket fuel pin cells. The core mean fission densities in driver and blanket fuel pins are provided in *Table VI*, and show higher mean fission density in driver fuel – as expected.

Table VI. Summary of Mean Fission Density in Driver & Blanket Fuel Cells .

Case	Mean Fission Density
Driver Fuel	$2.6290 \times 10^{-1} \pm 0.0002$
Blanket Fuel	$8.0632 \times 10^{-2} \pm 0.0002$

Heating was tallied in both driver and blanket fuel pins by using a Distributed Cell Filter [9] for the relevant cells and then plotted over the geometry. As driver and blanket fuel pins do not have the same radius, we are primarily interested in the volume averaged heating – i.e., heating density. Normalizing for cell volume shows substantially higher heating density per source particle in driver fuel. This is visualized in *Figure 2* over the geometry plot.

5. CONCLUSIONS

In this work we have developed a set of stylized benchmark problems for a Metal fuel configuration of the GE PRISM sodium cooled SMR as preliminary work towards validating the performance of a Novel Ultimate Heat Sink Device currently under development by [4]. To that end, a steady-state Neutronics model for three operation cases were developed – an uncontrolled case with all control rods withdrawn from the core, a critical case, and a controlled case with all control rods inserted. Publicly available geometry and material design information from General Electric documentation informed much of the benchmark development. In those areas where details were unavailable, reasonable estimates were extrapolated from other sources and designs. Complete core geometrical and material parameters were outlined with a treatment of relevant assumptions and simplifications. Eigenvalue and heating results from coupled neutron-photon calculations using OpenMC align with expectations.

This work aimed to develop the preliminary Neutronic benchmark models to add to the existing suite of full-core benchmark models used to test the performance of particle transport codes and serve as the basis for extension to more integrated modeling analysis. Detailed benchmark descriptions and results were successfully summarized and presented. In future work this will extend to both coupled neutron-photon transport results to get a high-fidelity heating profile of the core, as well as systems-level code integration to account for thermal feedback from particle cross-sections, coolant system parameters, and quasi-transient analysis of the leakage-based reactivity Gas Expansion Module used in this design.

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